

ENERGY-EFFICIENT NAVAL SHIPS OF THE FUTURE

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Summary

The U.S. Navy selected gas turbine propulsion for its most recent classes of cruisers, destroyers, and frigates because of weight, space, and performance advantages, and the ease of automation, of marine gas turbines. These plants, although currently less efficient than diesels and steam plants during certain operating modes, offer the long-range potential of significantly better fuel economy, through the development of new components and the adoption of a different design philosophy.

Presently, marine gas turbines are simple cycle engines and, for naval propulsion, are configured so that there is at least one per shaft (i.e., one engine cannot directly power multiple shafts to improve operating efficiency). Additionally, auxiliary electrical power is generated by turbine generators which are completely separate from the propulsion modules.

The development of a steam bottoming cycle for the LM-2500 gas turbine and the development of a regenerated cruise propulsion engine -- one which recovers exhaust heat to preheat combustion air -- offer the potential to improve engine cycle efficiencies by more than 30 percent. Electric drive transmission systems which employ either conventional electric motor technology or are superconductive (i.e., have magnets which are cryogenically cooled to 4°K) will permit arrangement flexibility, cross-connectability, and variable gas turbine-to-propeller speed ratio. Arrangement flexibility permits the construction of smaller, lighter ships because components are not constrained by shaft alignments. Cross-connectability allows multiple shafts to be driven by a single engine, therefore leading to more efficient part-power operation. The variable speed ratio lets the engine operate at its most efficient speed for any given power output.

Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) and Uninterruptible Power Supplies (UPS) will yield a 15-25 percent fuel savings for ship's service electric plants by eliminating the need to operate redundant turbine-generator sets to protect vital loads against loss of power. The BESS will provide emergency power to vital loads for the time necessary to bring a standby generator on line. It is also an essential element in any integrated system, such as that described below.

Auxiliary systems which include fresh water production, personnel hot water heating, galley heaters, air conditioning equipment, and space heaters may be either heat- or electrically-powered depending upon the optimum distribution of energy sources for a particular application. This optimum distribution is determined through integration of the propulsion, electrical power generation, and auxiliary systems of the ship for its mission requirements.

Integrating the propulsion and ship's service generating systems can offer significant energy savings. This can be achieved with either mechanical or electrical transmission systems, although electrical systems offer maximum opportunities. The central philosophy can be such that ship speed is controlled in the traditional manner, that is, through direct throttle control, or through the variation of propulsion generator and/or motor field excitation. In the latter

case, the propulsion gas turbine engine could be operated at constant speed, thereby greatly simplifying the auxiliary generator operation which would otherwise have to maintain a constant output frequency in spite of varying input speeds. Separate ship's service generator sets would be used only at low speeds or when the ship is not underway. It is this philosophy -- the utilization of the fewest prime movers and the use of all practical energy sources -- that is central to improved energy efficiency.

Introduction

The decision by the U.S. Navy in the late 1960s to select gas turbine propulsion for the SPRUANCE (DD-963) Class of destroyers represented a radical departure from traditional warship design. The considerations which led to this decision[1] were the ease of automation and the weight, space, and performance advantages of aircraft-derivative marine gas turbines. These advantages permitted substantial reductions in ship size and cost, reduced manning, and improved surveillance and detection systems performance, when compared to other candidate systems, such as conventional steam or diesel. A disadvantage, however, is the somewhat increased part-power fuel consumption of the gas turbine engines, owing in part to the specific configuration employed. The importance of this was just beginning to be felt in 1975, the year that the SPRUANCE was commissioned, as a result of the oil embargo of 1973-74. Marine diesel fuel which had been costing \$6.50 a barrel in 1973 was approaching \$30.00 a barrel. In 1983, it is now costing approximately \$50.00 a barrel.

The propulsion system arrangement of the SPRUANCE is shown in Figure 1. It consists of four gas turbines, each rated in excess of 20,000 horsepower, which are connected (two each) through reduction gears to controllable reversible pitch propellers (CRP). These propellers are used to provide a reversing capability because of the unidirectional nature of gas turbine engines, and to permit speed variations below 10 knots when the engines are operating at minimum (or idle) speeds. This type of plant, which is known as a split plant, because it was designed to have at least two engines in operation to power two shafts (i.e., shafts cannot be cross-connected), tends to have a higher part-load fuel consumption than plants which have some degree of flexibility. This can be seen in Figure 2, which compares the specific fuel consumption of the gas turbine plant with that of a 1,200 psi steam plant. At speeds below 20 knots, the characteristics of the steam plant become increasingly favorable, because it can be

Figure 1. DD-963 Propulsion Arrangement

Figure 2. Gas Turbine vs. Steam Plant Fuel Consumption

cross-connected, whereas the gas turbine ship requires that 40,000 horsepower be on line to provide 15,000 horsepower, or less, during cruising conditions. This situation can be corrected to the point that the gas turbine plant will be more efficient than the steam plant if it trails one shaft when cruising in this speed range. This practice, however, can be employed only during conditions when prudence and safety permit.

In the future, the evolution of new, highly efficient components and subsystems, and their employment in fully integrated system configurations, will permit the retention of the favorable aspects which led to the adoption of gas turbines for marine application, while at the same time yielding ships with lower fuel consumption over their full range of operations than any presently in the Fleet. A number of concepts currently being developed and some proposed configuration philosophies are presented in the following sections.

Propulsion Systems

The propulsion requirements of a naval combatant account for more than 60 percent of its fuel consumption. This fact relegates it to a position of prime importance when considering measures to improve ship operating efficiency. More importantly, however, the types of engines and transmission systems employed and the design philosophy invoked in many cases dictate how the rest of the ship is configured, and may in fact offer additional opportunities for fuel efficiency. The major concern for propulsion systems, as discussed above, is efficient cruise operation, since this is the configuration in which a ship spends most of its time. On the other hand, total installed power is dictated by top speed requirements.

Figure 3. RACER System Schematic

Three propulsion concepts presently under development offer significant opportunities for improved cruise-power efficiency, and for the design of fully integrated systems concepts. The first, which is termed RACER (Rankine Cycle Energy Recovery), is a steam bottoming cycle for the LM-2500 gas turbine shown conceptually in Figure 3[2]. The design goals of this system are to provide a 25 percent reduction in propulsion fuel consumption and to increase the ship's range by 1,000 nautical miles. It is being designed for maximum reliability and availability through use of a once-through boiler, passive water treatment, and corrosion-resistant materials. The steam turbine will produce up to 8,000 horsepower, depending upon the operating point of the LM-2500. This power can, in turn, be utilized in one of two ways: either to augment the gas turbine power on the same shaft (i.e., a series connection), or in an uneven distribution whereby one shaft would be powered by a gas turbine and the other by a steam turbine during cruise conditions. It is anticipated that the latter could be accomplished with minimal rudder correction, based upon trail shafting experience.

The second program is also intended to improve engine efficiency through regeneration. This involves the recovery of exhaust heat to preheat combustion air, thereby reducing the amount of heat that must be generated in the combustion process. This is shown schematically in Figure 4. For most aircraft-derivative marine gas turbines, an intercooler will be required to cool the inlet air between the low pressure and high pressure compressor stages. The attractive feature of the regenerated engine is that it uses only one working fluid, air, and the regenerator module can be designed to fit within existing exhaust stack dimensions, thus minimizing volume requirements. Cycle efficiencies comparable to those projected for RACER are anticipated for regenerated cruise engines.

Figure 4. Regenerated Gas Turbine Schematic

Presently, the Navy program to develop a regenerated engine in the 10,000 to 20,000 horsepower range is in the conceptual design stage. Variations of three separate engine types are being assessed. Two of the engine types are configured as regenerated and intercooled machines. The third is a low pressure ratio engine that does not require intercooling. Of the configurations studied to date, one has exhibited the best performance potential. This configuration is a 17,800 horsepower engine that is regenerated and intercooled and employs power turbine variable area nozzles to minimize power turbine inlet temperature variations over the operating range. The projected specific fuel consumption (SFC) of this engine compared with that of the simple cycle engine is presented in Figure 5, which shows that the specific fuel consumption of the regenerated engine, which is 15 percent less than that of the simple cycle engine at full power, is 32 percent less at 40 percent power (about 7,000 hp). This is significant, because maximum projected savings are in the power range of primary concern.

The third propulsion area does not involve the propulsion engines directly, but it does affect the means by which rotational power is transmitted to the propeller. This is electric drive. The principal advantages of this type of transmission system are: (1) it provides a capability to vary the ratio of turbine speed to propeller speed thereby allowing the gas turbines to operate at their most efficient speeds for any given power output; (2) it permits arrangement flexibility because the drive train components are connected by electrical cables and their relative positions are, therefore, not constrained by shaft alignments as are geared systems; (3) multiple shafts can be cross-connected to permit operation on a single engine at cruise speeds; and (4) it offers the opportunity to fully integrate the ship propulsion and auxiliary electric power generation functions of the ship. This latter point will be discussed at length later in this paper.

Electric drive systems can be either normally conductive (conventional AC or DC machinery) or superconductive where the magnets are immersed in liquid helium and operate at a temperature of 4°K. At this temperature, materials such as niobium titanium become superconductive; that is, they exhibit a phenomenon where their resistance to the flow of electrical current decreases to almost zero. This permits the development of electric generators and motors that are much smaller in size and weight than conventional machines. A comparison of a superconductive electric drive with an equivalent mechanical system[3] such as that presented in Figure 1 above, showed that a nine percent reduction in ship volume and a 25 percent reduction in

Figure 5. Regenerated vs. Simple Cycle SFC Profiles

Figure 6. Podded Superconductive Electric Drive

installed power, with no reduction in payload, speed, range, or other mission capabilities, were achievable with the superconductive system. A second study[4] attempted to exploit the full arrangement flexibility potential of this type of system by removing the propulsion motors from the ship's hull and placing them in pods or nacelles as shown in Figure 6. Using this type of arrangement, a 16.6 percent reduction in displacement and a 24.8 percent reduction in fuel load were projected. This should be compared to the 16 percent reduction in fuel load achievable by trail shafting. The electric drive gains result from removal of the propulsion motor from the hull with the consequent elimination of in-hull shafting, and from the ability to locate the propulsion turbines on the main deck, thereby significantly reducing inlet and exhaust stack weight and volume.

Electrical and Auxiliary Systems

The propulsion arrangement shown in Figure 1 requires the provision of separate turbine generators for the production of ship's service electrical power. Whereas the speed of the propulsion turbines is proportional to the ship's speed desired, the ship's service engines are operated at constant speed to preclude frequency variations. Additionally, to minimize the possibility of a complete loss of electrical power due to the loss of a ship's service engine, at least two units are operated at all times. In the case of the DD-963, this means that for a cruise-condition electrical power requirement of 1,500-2,000 kW, at least 4,000 kW of capacity is on line. The ship's service engines are, therefore, operating at between 40 and 50 percent load, which is highly inefficient. One solution to this is to provide an emergency back-up power source which will permit the elimination of the redundant turbine generator by being able to provide power to vital loads during the period necessary to start another engine in the event of loss of the on-line engine. A concept presently being developed for this purpose is the Battery Energy Storage System (BESS). The BESS is shown schematically in Figure 7. It stores up to two

Figure 7. BESS System Schematic

Figure 8. UPS System Schematics

mega-watt-minutes of power in secondary storage batteries. These batteries are automatically switched on-line when an emergency occurs. Since it utilizes off-line storage, it has very low power losses, but it could be of medium to large size if the charge rate required becomes too high. At present, allowable charge time is 24 hours, which yields a practical system size. The most challenging aspect of this system concept, however, is the switching circuit which must switch from the normal to emergency mode in less than 1/2 cycle. This requirement is dictated by the power interruption susceptibility of the various electronic equipments.

The system switching requirement can be eliminated through the use of a UPS approach. This type of system provides continuous power as shown in the two schematics of Figure 8. The first, which is the conventional UPS approach, uses available technology. It would, however, be of a large size and generate high power losses because of the need to rectify and then invert to type I power all of the generator output. The second eliminates that problem by permitting the UPS to "float" on-line. This, however, creates a requirement to parallel the converter with the generator, which would require successful R&D to accomplish.

Auxiliary equipment such as that for the production of fresh water and for heating and cooling can be either electrically-powered or heat-powered. The best means of providing all of the required services must be determined for each ship type based upon all of the available energy sources and sinks and the ship's mission requirements. In general, the options can be separated into three groups: all electric, part heat recovery, and all heat recovery.

All Electric -- This would involve the use of systems such as reverse osmosis desalination for fresh water production, electrically driven centrifugal- or screw-compressor air conditioning, and the use of resistance heating for personnel hot water,

galley heaters, and space heaters. It is attractive when exhaust heat is being recovered to improve the cycle efficiencies of propulsion and/or ship's service prime movers (RACER or regenerated engines), and it eliminates steam plumbing and reduces maintenance.

Part Heat Recovery -- This type of concept could use exhaust heat recovery units to provide steam or hot water to major users such as flash distillation units for fresh water production, and heat-powered air conditioning. However, it could retain the use of electric resistance heaters for the remaining functions. Its advantages are that it permits the use of some recovered heat for improving cycle efficiency but offers an alternative to the large electric loads presented by major auxiliary systems, and minimizes the plumbing which would be associated with more extensive use of recovered heat.

All Heat Recovery -- This option would eliminate all electrical resistance heating, as well as the electrically-driven air conditioning and desalination plants, thereby reducing generator size. It does have the disadvantage of complex piping throughout the ship and is, therefore, impractical for most applications.

Integrated Systems Concepts

In the preceding paragraphs, high efficiency components and system arrangements have been described which individually can contribute to more fuel-efficient future ships. The maximum gains, however, will be realized when these are assembled into total system concepts that are specifically directed at and optimized for the applications of interest. Three illustrative configurations are described below.

The simplest system concept which integrates the ship's service electrical system with the propulsion system is a variant of the present mechanical drive system shown in Figure 9. In this system, a Variable Speed, Constant Frequency (VSCF) generator accepts inputs which have a rotational frequency that varies according to the speed of the propulsion engines and converts it to a constant (60 Hz) alternating current (AC) output. This combination of propulsion and auxiliary power generation functions is the essential aspect of what is termed an integrated system. Because the VSCF cannot provide adequate power at very low ship speeds, a ship's service generator set is included to augment the VSCF as necessary. The BESS is available to provide emergency power to vital loads. It thereby permits the ship's total power requirement during peacetime cruise conditions, to be met by a single engine. This concept also includes a cruise gas turbine which ideally would either be regenerated or include a RACER bottoming cycle, and a reverse-reduction gear. This permits replacement of the CRP propeller with a fixed

Figure 9. Mechanical Drive System

Figure 10. AC Induction Motor Drive System

pitch (FP) propeller that has a delivered power requirement approximately 10 percent less than that of the CRP for a twin-screw destroyer.

Two other concepts demonstrate how a conventional electric drive might be employed to further enhance fuel efficiency through variable reduction ratio, cross-connectability, and arrangement flexibility. The first of these is the AC system shown in Figure 10. This system uses the same ship's service electrical generation and distribution system as the mechanical system. For propulsion, however, the cruise gas turbine drives a conventional air-cooled 2-pole alternator. Propulsion motors are air-cooled squirrel-cage induction motors which drive fixed-pitch propellers by way of two-stage planetary gears.

The second electric drive system is one which employs DC propulsion motors as shown in Figure 11. This system additionally employs a different control scheme than that utilized for the AC case. For the DC system, the cruise prime mover is operated at constant speed, thus enabling the use of a conventional ship's service generator, thereby eliminating the complexity of the VSCF. Ship speed control for the DC system is accomplished through the variation of field excitation of either the propulsion alternator or propulsion motor. On the other hand, in the AC case, ship speed is controlled by direct throttle control, and alternator field variation is required only for low speed operation below the idle speed of the cruise gas turbine. The propulsion alternator in the DC system would be the same as that for the AC system, although rectified. The DC propulsion motor would be a liquid-cooled homopolar motor which might employ liquid metal current collectors for enhanced current-carrying capability. This approach has an added advantage -- the ship's service generator can function as a motor to power the ship at low speeds if required.

The above system concepts, which are generally near-term in nature, are examples of how machinery plants can be configured to maximize efficiency through the use of integrated design techniques. Many variations of this basic philosophy are possible, including the use of superconductive systems as well as high-efficiency hull appendages and propulsors. Those

best suited for a given application, however, are determined by the type of ship involved and the mission requirements of that ship.

Conclusion

Energy-efficient naval ships of the future can retain the attractive characteristics inherent in gas turbine propulsion plants while offering vastly improved opportunities for reduced fuel consumption with no loss of mission effectiveness, through utilization of:

- o Exhaust heat recovery systems that improve the cycle efficiencies of gas turbines by greater than 30 percent at part load;
- o Transmission arrangements that permit reductions over 16 percent in displacement and 24 percent in fuel load relative to conventional configurations;
- o Energy storage systems that reduce the fuel consumption for auxiliary electric power generation by 15-25 percent through elimination of redundant units;
- o Design of auxiliary machinery systems which make optimum use of all available sources of energy; and
- o Machinery design techniques which enable the total ship to operate as an integrated system.

References

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Figure 11. DC Electric Drive System